

trial was in a split-plot design with three replications. N was applied as neem cake-coated urea at 20%, coal tar-coated urea at 1%, urea supergranules (USG), and prilled urea. When N was split applied, 50% was basal and the rest was in 2 equal splits 15 and 35 d after

transplanting.

Maximum plant height was with 75 kg N/ha as USG, which was at par with 50 kg N as USG. USG and coal tar-coated urea produced maximum panicles per hill and panicle length. USG produced best grain filling and

highest weight followed by neem cake-coated urea (see table).

The interaction of N level and sources significantly influenced grain yield (see table). USG performed best, followed by neem cake-coated urea. *S*

Effect of transplanting schedule and postharvest time intervals for threshing on rice grain yield and head rice recovery

P. S. Gill and H. N. Shahi, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Rice Research Station (RRS), Kapurthala 144601, India

We evaluated the effect of transplanting schedule and postharvest time intervals for threshing on grain yield and head rice recovery of different rices at the PAU RRS, Kapurthala.

Thirty-five-day-old seedlings of medium-duration Jaya; medium-duration, fine-grained PR106; and short-duration, long-and-slender grained PR103 were transplanted on 1 and 15 Jun (early), 30 Jun, 15 Jul (optimum), or 30 Jul (late). The experiment was in a randomized block design with four replications. At harvest, the main plot was divided into five subplots. The harvested crop was left in the field in small piles for threshing at different times.

1. Effect of transplanting schedule on grain yield of three rices.

2. Effect of transplanting schedule and postharvest time intervals for threshing on head rice recovery (raw and parboiled) of 3 rices.

All varieties yielded highest when planted on 30 Jun (Fig. 1). Yield reduction was most severe when PR 103 (short duration) was transplanted 1 Jun and medium-duration Jaya and PR106 were transplanted 15 and 30 Jul. At optimum transplanting time, varieties had high dry matter production, tiller and spikelet fertility, and 1,000-grain weight.

Labor shortages often require a harvested crop to remain in the field for several days before threshing. The difference in day and night temperature and night dew formation cause cracks and fissures in the grain, and therefore breakage during milling. Threshing within 2 d of harvesting gave significantly higher head yield than delayed threshing (Fig. 2).

The early transplanted crop matured on 23 Sep. It was exposed to high temperatures and heavy dew formation during late development and at harvest, which caused more sun cracks and poor head recovery percentage. PR106 had 4-

15% higher head yield (Fig. 2) under different treatments than Jaya and PR103. Head yield was significantly higher with parboil milling than with raw milling. Our findings suggest that

proper manipulation of preharvest and postharvest agronomic practices can ensure greater head rice recovery without requiring additional economic liability. *ℒ*

Effect of levels and modified forms of urea and ammonium chloride on lowland rice

V. Murali, R. Kulandaivelu, and T. Y. Reddy, Agronomy Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 3, India

We studied the effect of levels and forms of urea and ammonium chloride on lowland rice yield in a 1983 field experiment. Co 37 was planted in kharif and IR20 in rabi. Soil was a clay loam. In kharif it contained 225-19.1-470 kg available NPK/ha, with pH 8.2 and EC 0.3 mmho/cm. In rabi it contained 201-18.9-515 kg available NPK with pH 8.2 and EC 0.25 mmho/cm.

Treatments included three forms each urea and ammonium chloride: supergranules, granulated compost, and prilled. N was applied at 0.40, 80, or 120 kg/ha. Ammonium chloride supergranules were made locally with a hand-operated granulizer. Granulated compost was made by mixing urea or ammonium chloride with farmyard manure using a fishmeal pelletizer.

Prilled urea and ammonium chloride were applied in equal splits at last

Yield and yield components as influenced by levels and modified forms of N fertilizer, Coimbatore, India.

N source and level (kg/ha)	Kharif (Jun-Sep)			Rabi (Oct-Feb)		
	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Ammonium chloride</i>						
Prilled	421	85	4.3	435	83	3.7
Granulated compost	421	84	3.9	435	82	3.6
Supergranules	438	87	4.8	458	86	4.2
<i>Urea</i>						
Prilled	421	84	4.3	436	83	3.7
Granulated compost	421	84	3.9	435	82	3.6
Supergranules	438	87	4.8	459	86	4.2
CD 5%	11	0	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.1
<i>Levels of N</i>						
40	345	80	3.1	318	79	2.7
80	406	82	4.2	435	82	3.7
120	458	86	4.6	411	86	4.3
CD 5%	485	92	5.5	488	87	4.8
CD 5%	8	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.1

puddling and maximum tillering. Supergranules and granulated compost were placed at 5-cm depth 10 d after transplanting. PK at 26 and 48 kg/ha was applied as superphosphate and muriate of potash at last puddling. PK content of farmyard manure was considered in the granulated compost treatments.

Applying 120 kg N/ha in any form gave significantly higher yields than other N levels. Urea and ammonium chloride performed equally well, and supergranules performed better than granulated compost, perhaps because the compost took longer to decompose and release N to the crop (see table). *ℒ*

Efficiency of different nitrogen fertilizers on rice

S. S. Kolhe and B. N. Mitra, Agricultural Engineering Department, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur 721302, India

We studied the efficiency of different N fertilizers on rice in 1980 wet season (Jul-Oct). Pusa 33 was planted on a lateritic sandy clay loam with pH 5.4, 0.380% organic C, CEC 8.70 meq/100 g soil, 0.041% total N, 4 ppm available P, and 0.048% total K. A no-N control and three sources of N were applied at three levels (see table). All plots received 26-50

Influence of different N sources and levels on rice grain yield, Kharagpur, India.

N (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)					Mean
	Control (no N)	Urea at planting	Urea in 3 splits	Urea supergranule (1-g size)	Sulfur-coated urea	
40		2.8	2.8	3.4	2.6	2.9
80		3.3	3.5	3.8	3.5	3.5
120		3.7	4.3	4.4	4.2	4.1
Mean	2.3	3.3	3.5	3.9	3.4	

LSD (P = 0.05)
 For sources including control 0.25
 For N level 0.14
 For two sources means for the same level 0.34
 For two levels means for the same source 0.29

kg PK/ha at transplanting. The experiment was in a split-plot design

with four replications with N sources in main plot and N levels in subplots.